

ADVERTISING EFFECTIVENESS WITH REFERENCE TO BIG BAZAAR

BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA

HOD and ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF MBA

LINGARAJ APPA ENGINEERING COLLEGE BIDAR-585403

bhadrappabhavimani@gmail.com

Orcid id-0000-0003-3214-7261

ABSTRACT

Customers preferences are changing, the market scenario is also change every once in the new while. The marketplace circumstance is altogether various these days using the marketplace circumstance before 1990. Presently there usually are numerous aspects that purpose a altering business industry situation. It can client paying and preference, which usually purchases accessible changes. The particular pay stage of people has altered; the design of life and usually the social class associated with individuals happen to be changed over now a lot more than typically the particular past times. You may find adjustments in the particular market about the world today. Advancement is 1 of usually the core stage, which usually have been in cost of transforming business field worldview. Typically the existing age does not always rely after the marketplace industry concerning the cap plus considerably with the retail string. These days you discover the particular new time period in the particular market with the opening associated with various retail establishments, hypermarkets, stop customers, shopping malls, brand name stores and claim to popularity shops. In this era shopping, it is distressing, however it's smarter to be able to be a superior miracle now. This study will depend after studies directed by simply hypermarket advertise clients referred to as huge markets. Enormous bazaar is another sort of industry, which has been inside India since 1994. This specific is a sort regarding market in an variety of items that is available on one rooftop. Physique out how to uncover about deciding client curiosity for big bazaar and typically the amount of consumer loyalty inside enormous markets. The exploration will locate the current status of any huge business center and decide typically the present commercial center. This specific market field study can assist us with understanding typically the flavor of sustenance in addition to client inclinations now. That will help figure typically the necessities and needs regarding clients.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Big Bazaar is an Indian retail vicinity propelled by means of a hypermarket set up sarvesh, rebate shops, and shops. The retail chain turned into set up by means of Kishore Biyani below the essential affiliation of the Future Group, recognized for its brilliant enthusiasm for the retail and style vicinity inside India. Huge Bazaar is usually likewise a chain regarding Food Bazaar, Fashion inside Big Bazaar (curtailed since and Zone E where it's miles located under one rooftop, whilst even more youthful sister from retail store locations, as an example, Brand Manufacturer, Townhouse, Central, ozone, in addition to so on.).

Placed in 2001, Big Bazaar is probably the maximum pro and most significant hypermarket advertise in Of india, with 250+ stores above a hundred and 20 or so city communities and villages in the country.Huge Bazaar become hooked up inside 2001 by making use of Kishore, founder and CEO of typically the determine company, Future Party. Indian entertainer, Salty in addition to previous skipper of typically the Indian cricket organization, Mahendra Singh Dhoni have strongly suggested the top Bazaar's vertical type.

The offspring of Tripura, Barkathal became rationally bothered by making use of burglary with typically the aid of Big Bazaar, Agartala earlier than many folks who drove the youthful girl to suicide inside her domestic. Numerous Sayapara wings dissent on typically the shopping center in Agartala to arraign equity.

1.2 INDUSTRY PROFILE

Retailing

Selling is an trade among a merchant and the consumer for character usage. It does exclude trades between manufacturers, buying companies, buying governments and buying additional wholesalers. A save provides merchandise from the producer and after that offers the same for the provide up customer for minimum benefit.

Retailing covers almost all sporting events that are usually introduced to the primary customers for the institution of school and domestic. Make this by using dealing with the accessibility of full-size scale versatility and grant customers with a normally little scale. Affiliates are people/institutions which are certified to get to merchandise or product or administrations for end customers. Affiliates are an absolute necessity and can not be killed. The Indian retail industry is gradually heat, as greater people pay for comparable clients. Real retailers are Pantaloon Retail, Shoppers Stop, Reliance, and so forth..,

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW WITH RESEARCH GAP

1. Focuses and Contrail (1946) have led thinks around on employment success with regards to the conjugal fame of employees and found mating expert as considerably greater paintings than nonmembers.
2. Inflow (1951) expressed that employees had been disillusioned with the start instances of the administration and the initial two years of management had the maximum energizing impact on employment fulfillment.
- 3.Three. Talachi (1960) says that lower paintings achievement have to make bigger turnover and non-attendance.
4. Shoukry and Otis (1964) clarify that the degree of career achievement increments in early paintings and diminishes the terminal time body.
5. Gannon and Hendrickson (1967) direct exploratory investigations on career course and occupation fulfillment of managers utilized within the retail commercial enterprise as one of

the government or employees. These discoveries exhibit that ladies are steadily all right with paintings while high-acting work is high.

6. Blum plus Naylor (1968) clarify that will the level of fulfillment plus obligation that could work will be the aftereffect from the particular mentalities the representatives create to their duties, in order to additives diagnosed with their own work and to the particular general population.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The particular examination paintings is an attribute investigation, and is expected to provide fundamental facts directed research purposes. This particular is an exploration give consideration dependent on the important information and the breakthroughs may be joined after a specific decisive exam has been finished.

Set up of a venture record and last exam is an entire system which accomplished in a few ranges. In this manner via the exploration system there are some troubles uncovered by way of analysts, at every development. In this exploration we can expect those busting factors.

3.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

- In the generation retail shop are served as evidence so as to carry the transaction, signing and becomes hectic activity. The companies are always striving to win the customers heart and the customers by the business man are said to be king and the king never bargains.
- As big bazaar is the retail shop and a departmental store to rise the money in a conservative manner i. e they have been assembled with a punch line
- “Isse sasta auraccha kahin nahi”.
- They come out with many offers as per the customer needs and benefits. Promotional activity plays a very prominent role to make aware of the things in market, to attract customers, to sell products and this study of promotional activity help to give a clear idea

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the different medias used by big bazaar for advertisement
- To Determine the effectiveness of the each media
- To study consumer perception towards advertisement of big bazaar
- To understand schemes and offers provided by big bazaar
- To know the impact of advertisement on sales

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The range of perception , the inquiry, the investigation has been minutely studied only to the activity of big bazaar
- The scope of project work is to get the opinions from respondents on the issue mentioned earlier.
- It helps in increase of customers productivity.
- It helps in achieving the organization goal.
- It helps in growth of the organization.
- It is confined to the dual cities of Hyderabad and is limited to the city areas because the respondents are the subscribers of BIG BAZAAR offerings is one shape or the opposite.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY ,HYPOTHESIS.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

Data collection :

Data collection is one of the technique of the records from different assets.

Method of information collection:

The technique of statistics series are of two types and they're ,primary information and secondary statistics.

Primary records:

Primary facts collection is first and primary technique ,that's used to accumulate initial material at some stage in the studies process.

Secondary records :

Secondary facts manner the ones statistics which can be already available this is the records which has been already series and analyzed by means of a person else. These statistics may be collected from books, workplace, journals, reports and business enterprise policies

The research approach : Survey method.

The research instruments: The instruments used for the research are questionnaires.

The respondents: The employees of the Big Bazaar Bidar.

Sampling method:

Sampling method is a very important part of the research process. Sampling is the method of choosing unit from a residents of concern.

Here size of the sample is 50 employees and the technique used in this study is convenience sampling.

4.ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1HAVE YOU SEEN BIG BAZAAR ADVERTISEMENT?

PARTICULARS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	46	92
NO	4	8
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPRETATION.

Above the graph show the table Yes is 92 % and than No is 8% . it

4.2 HOW WOULD YOU RATE BIG BAZAAR ADVERTISEMENT COMPARED WITH OTHERS YOU HAVE SEEN.?

PERTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Much better	9	18
Better	39	78
More or less the same	2	4
Total	50	100

INTERPRETATION.

Above the graph show the Table much batter in 18 %and than batter is 78 %and than more or less the same is 4 %.

4.3 HOW DID THE ADVERTISEMEN DESCRIBE THE PRODUCT /SERVICE?

PERTICULAR	RESPOINDENTS	PERCENTEGE
Very bad	0	
Bad	2	4
Average	25	50
Well	23	46
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPRETATION

Above the graph show the table very bad is 0 %and than a bad is a 4 %.and than a Average is 50%.and then a well is a46 %

4.4 BASED ON THIS ADVERTISEMENT ABOUT (ENTIRE PRODUCT/SERVICE) WOULD YOU BUY IT?

PURTICULARSR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
---------------------	--------------------	-------------------

Sure yes	36	72
Probably yes	9	18
May Be	5	10
Probably Not	0	0
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPRETATION.

Above the graph show the table sure yes is 72 %.and than is a probably yes is 18 %.and than a may be is10 %. and than a probably not is a 0% .

4.5 DO YOU AXCEPT THIS PRODUCT /SERVICE TO BE VERY DIFFERENT FROM OTHERS IN THIS MARKET?

PURTICULAR	RESPOINDENTS	PERCENTAGE
It will be very different	13	26
It will be something different	24	48
It will be quite similar	11	22
It will be the same	2	4
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPRETATION.

Above the graph show the table it will be different is 26%. And then it will be something different is 48%. and then it will be quite similar is 22% and then it will be the same 4% it.

4.6 HAVE YOU FOUND CREDIBLE THE AFFIRMATIONS MADE IN THE ADVERTISEMENT ABOUT THE PRODUCT /SERVICE?

PURTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERSENTAGE
Total credible	21	42
Quite credible	24	48
Neither credible non credible	3	6
Quite incredible	2	4
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table Total ly credible is 42% and their Quit credible is 48 % and than Neither credible non credible is 6% and than Quit credible is 4 % it.

4.7 WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING WORDS OR PHASES WOULD YOU TO DESCRIBE THIS ADVERTISEMENT TO A FRIEND

PURTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Attractive	36	72
Draws attractive	9	18
Boring	2	4
Intelligent	3	6
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table Attractive is 72 %. and than Draws attention is 18 %. and than is Boring is 4 % .and than Intelligent is 6% it.

4.8 ACCORDING TO WHAT YOU HAVE SEEN IN THE ADVERTISEMENT WHAT TYPE OF PERSON DO YOU BELIEVE WOULD USE THIS PRODUCT /SERVICE?

PURTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
More woman will use it	7	14
More men will use it	5	10
Both men and women	37	74
Sophisticated peole	1	2
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table more women will use it is 14 %, and than a More men will use it 10%. and than is Both men and women is 74 %. and than Sophisticated people is 2 % it.

4.9 HAVE YOU USED AT BIG BAZAAR PRODUCT IT BEFORE?

PERTICULAR	RESPOINDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	40	80
NO	10	20
TOTAL	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table yes is 80 % and than a No is 20 % it .

4.10 ACCORDING TO WHAT YOU HAVE SEEN IN THE ADVERTISEMENT?

PURTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTEGE
More women will use	3	6
More men will use it	7	14
Both men and women	39	78
Calm people	1	2
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table More women will use it 6% and than More men will use it is 14 %. and than both Men and women is 78 %. and than Clam peole is 2 %.

4. 11 FROM THE FOLLOWING WHICH ARE THE OFFERS ARE YOU AWARE

PERTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Great exchange offer	33	66
Buy one get one free	16	32
Buy3 appeareals at999	1	2
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table is Great exchange offer 66 % and than Buy one get free 32 % and than is Buy3 appeareals at 999 is 2%.it

4.12 HOW DO YOU COME TO KNOW ABOUT BIG BAZAAR OUTET?

PERTICULAR	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
News paper	11	22
Television	7	14
Radio	0	0
Internet	10	20
Friends	22	44
Total	50	100

INTERPRITATION.

Above the graph show the table News paper is 22%. and than television is 14 % and than Radio is 0 % and than Internet is 20 % and than Friends is 44 %. it

5.1 FINDINGS:

- Most of the responded rated big bazaar advertisement is better then compared with other
- May only a both men & women have seen in the advertisement
- More number customer used big bazaar product before
- Most of the customer know great exchange offer
- Most of the responded have come to know effect big bazaar out let through source of news paper

5.2 CONCLUSION

From the above study I concluded that, employees involvement is one of the most important for the growth of the organization .

In the marketplace there are excessive employee involvement in all elements. Employees are based on huge bazaars. The employees are pleased with the recognition of their paintings by control

More than all personnel are happy and happy with the involvement of personnel in BIG BAZAAR BIDAR.

5.3 SUGGESTION:

- BIG BAZAAR should increase the coverage of its all services i.e. dairy and agree and retail also, services by installing more at strategic points
- The quality of the retail service needs to be improved in terms of clarity and connectivity.
- BIG BAZAAR need to pass for retail benefits instead of rivalry and ought to attention on individual clients and non-enterprise customers.
- BIG BAZAAR need to forcefully suggest an concept in one-of-a-kind media and need to consciousness on space, road seems and electronic media.
- Attractive plans to offer accommodation shops ought to be propelled to draw inside more players

REFERENCES

1. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , PERFORMANCE AFFECTING FACTORS OF INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 607-621, Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya.pdf>
2. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY AFFECTING FACTORS IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI), Vol.- 12 Issue -03, June 2021, PAGE No : 603-620, Available at: <https://www.tojqi.net/index.php/journal/article/view/791/242>
3. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 631-642 Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya-1.pdf>
4. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com) , Volume: 2, Issue: 5, May 2021, Page No : 184-194. Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2105025.pdf>
5. Bhadrappa Haralayya ; P. S. Aithal . "Study on Model and Camel Analysis of Banking" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals ,Volume 4 ,Issue 11 ,May 2021 Page 244-259.

Available at <https://irejournals.com/paper-details/1702750>

6. Bhadrappa Haralayya and Aithal, P. S.. “Analysis of cost efficiency on scheduled commercial banks in India”. International Journal of Current Research, Volume 13, Issue 06, June 2021, pp 17718-17725 Available at:
<https://www.journalcra.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/41580.pdf>
7. Bhadrappa Haralayya and P. S. Aithal, “A Study On Structure and Growth of Banking Industry in India”, International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management , Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2021. Page no 225–230. Available at:
<https://www.journals.resaim.com/ijresm/article/view/778/749>.
8. Bhadrappa Haralayya, Retail Banking Trends in India ,International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), Volume: 9, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 3730-3732. Available At
http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Bhadrappa_Haralayyaqscw.pdf
9. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR : A TOBIT REGRESSION ANALYSIS", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijedr.org), Vol.6, Issue 6, June-2021, page no.1 - 6, , Available
:<http://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR2106001.pdf>
10. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, flusserstudies, Volume 30, June 2021, Page No:1068-1080, Available at: <https://flusserstudies.org/archives/801>
11. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, June-2021 ,Page no: 159 – 164, Available:
http://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151514_PAPER.pdf
12. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , STUDY OF BANKING SERVICES PROVIDED BY BANKS IN INDIA, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), Volume: 2, Issue: 6, Year: June 2021, Page No : 06-12, Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2106002.pdf>.
13. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANK PERFORMANCE USING CAMEL APPROACH", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (www.jetir.org | UGC and issn Approved), Vol.8, Issue 5, May-2021, page no 305-314, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105840.pdf>
14. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, ANALYSIS OF BANK PRODUCTIVITY

USING PANEL CAUSALITY TEST, Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Volume 50, Issue 6, June-2021 , Page no: 1 – 16, Available at:
<https://app.box.com/s/o71lh776opeypauvzucp9esntjwur9zf>

15. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, INTER BANK ANALYSIS OF COST EFFICIENCY USING MEAN, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET), Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021 ,Page no: 6391-6397, Available at: http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2021/june/97_INTER_NC1.pdf
16. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX OF BANKS BY HMTFP AND FPTFP, Science, Technology and Development Journal, Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021, Page no: 190-203, Available at: <http://journalstd.com/gallery/23-june2021.pdf>
17. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY AGGREGATE LEVEL, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume 13, Issue 6, June- 2021 ,Page no: 296-314, available at: <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/28-june2021.pdf>
18. Bhadrappa Haralayya, P S Aithal, "ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY DISAGGREGATE LEVEL", International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), Volume.9, Issue 6, June 2021, pp.b488-b502, Available at :<http://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2106187.pdf>
19. Haralayya B. Importance of CRM in Banking and Financial Sectors Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021, 6(1): 8-9
20. Haralayya B. How Digital Banking has Brought Innovative Products and Services to India. Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021; 6(1): 16-18
21. Haralayya B. Top 5 Priorities That will Shape The Future of Retail Banking Industry in India. Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management 2021; 8(1&2): 17-18.
22. Haralayya B. Millennials and Mobile-Savvy Consumers are Driving a Huge Shift in The Retail Banking Industry. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 17-19
23. Haralayya B. Core Banking Technology and Its Top 6 Implementation Challenges. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 25-27
24. Nitesh S Vibhute ; Dr. Chandrakant B. Jewargi ; Dr. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Non-Performing Assets of Public Sector Banks" Iconic Research And Engineering

Journals Volume 4, Issue, 12 June 2021, Page 52-61 Available at
<https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702767.pdf>

25. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa and Saini, Shrawan Kumar, An Overview on Productive Efficiency of Banks & Financial Institution (2018). International Journal of Research, Volume 05 Issue 12, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837503>
26. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Review on the Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country (2018). Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, Volume 04 Issue 05, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837496>
27. Basha, Jeelan and Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Performance Analysis of Financial Ratios - Indian Public Non-Life Insurance Sector (April 30, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837465>.
28. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, The Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country With Special Reference to Banks & Financial Institution (april 30, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844432> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844432>
29. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Study on Performance of Foreign Banks in India (APRIL 2, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844403> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844403>
30. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-Finance and the Financial Services Industry (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844405>
31. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-payment - An Overview (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844409> .
32. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Customer Satisfaction at M/s Sindol Bajaj Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4 ,Issue 12, June 2021, Page 157-169 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702792.pdf>
33. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Ratio Analysis at NSSK, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 170-182 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702793.pdf>
34. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Financial Statement Analysis of Shri Ram City Union Finance" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 183-196 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702794.pdf>
35. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Employee Job Satisfaction at Big Bazaar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 197-206 Available at:

- <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702795.pdf>
36. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Effect of Branding on Consumer Buying Behaviour at Vijay Bharat Motors Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 207-222 Available at:
<https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702796.pdf>
37. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Customer Perceptions Guru Basava Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 223-231 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/17027972.pdf>
38. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Loans and Advances for DCC Bank Main Branch Nayakaman, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 232-242 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702798.pdf>
39. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Work Life Balance of Employees at Karanja Industries Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 243-254 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702799.pdf>
40. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Working Capital Management at TVS Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 255-265 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702800.pdf>
41. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Testing Weak Form Efficiency of Indian Stock Market – An Empirical Study on NSE (April 30, 2021). Emerging Global Strategies for Indian Industry (ISBN: 978-81-910118-7-6), 2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837488>
42. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Top 10 Ways to Improve the Communication Skills (JUNE 20, 2016). Available at
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844410> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844410>
43. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Multi-Inter-Trans Disciplinary Research Towards Management and Commerce (July 25, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3847404>

